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28.9.2025

Evidence of Abuse of Power During a Complaint Process Related to a EU Call for Projects

Dear all,

Dear members and offices of the European Parliament,

Dear members and offices of the European Commission,

Dear members of the European Ombudsman,

Dear members of the EACEA,

In 2023, António Guterres, current Secretary-General of the United Nations, highlighted that estimates indicate we will be reaching only 15% of planned SDGs targets by 2030, and many are going in reverse.

At the same time, multiple studies and meta-analyses have observed a progressive decline of breakthrough innovation after the 1970s by 5% per year.

In the attached document, I provide evidence of a case of power abuse in European institutions related to a public EU call for projects in the innovation sector, defined as rejection through inadequate reasoning as indicated by European guidelines on *Complaints About Proposal Rejection*.

The applicant submitted a project proposal to the Creative Innovation Lab 2021 managed by Creative Europe. The applicant complained about an abuse of power by the MEDIA Strand in dealing with his redress request, defined by Europe as inadequate reasoning of the conclusions. The European Ombudsman refused to open an investigation stating that there were "no grounds" to open an enquiry.

My investigation, initiated after accessing files under Regulation 1049/2001, documents a pattern by both the EACEA and the European Ombudsman of **failing to address the core argument** of the complainant. Specifically, the MEDIA Strand showed a pattern of avoiding the core argument—the correct integration of the audiovisual sector in the project

application—first by mentioning a post-hoc set of restrictions, and then through unsupported speculative reasoning (constituting abuse of power). The European Ombudsman, in turn, granted credence to this speculation without asking for evidence and without acknowledging that the complainant's core argument remains unresolved.

The episode highlights important challenges related to innovation and sustainability, as the rejected project has been acknowledged as a top innovation in multiple European competitions, by initiatives like the **Horizon-2020 CLIC Startup Competition** (top-9 international projects), the **Italian Alliance for Sustainable Development** (Innovability School, top-14 Italian projects in all sectors), and the **Startup Europe Accelerathon** (top-4 European projects in the Cultural & Creative Industries). It should be noted that Startup Europe Accelerathon is an initiative by Startup Europe, a program created by the European Commission to identify and promote those projects that best support European priorities like LIFE or the New European Bauhaus.

This presents important challenges at a general level, as the UN has highlighted our difficulties in reaching our planned targets, and it is a question whether we can actually reach our targets if some promising ideas risk being sabotaged from within our institutions due to inattentive reviews or abuses of power. If that were true, it would not be surprising that we cannot reach our SDGs. In particular, there is a general consensus that we do not have much time and we should speed up our efforts in relation to sustainable development, so losing our chances to innovate due to internal errors may cost us a lot.

The question, now, is how long it will take for these abuses of power to steal our future. The problem highlighted by this episode is serious. Unfortunately, I have not received any support from other actors to ensure that procedures for meaningful innovation are respected, and complaints about proposal rejection are correctly addressed to ensure that promising ideas are not sabotaged by errors or mistakes. I question whether this collective silence around the episode and the lack of support in ensuring a fair resolution to my complaint should be considered a form of institutional betrayal.

I am a whistleblower. As Tom Devine from the Government Accountability Project would describe them: “Who are these whistleblowers? They’re people who use freedom of speech to challenge abuses of power that betray the public trust.” To provide further public context on these systemic challenges, I maintain a dedicated YouTube channel, “**Sliding Doors**,” discussing topics of innovation and power abuse in research. The relevant content can be found here: [<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ms7zLFAQqTs>].

This whistleblowing is everything I could do to serve my nation, my people, my children, and the future, to ensure the creation of an ecosystem that truly innovates meaningfully, for the sake of everyone. As promoted by the John Maddox Prize, it is important, even

through difficulties, to make sure that administrations work and design policies on the basis of evidence.

Given the systemic failures documented in the attached report, the public interest and institutional integrity necessitate a comprehensive response from the relevant governors and institutions. I strongly encourage them to include steps toward redress comparable to the damage incurred, and the launch of a large-scale investigation into these systemic failures and instances of abuse of power. The attached document is written in the third person. Alongside this public disclosure, a copy of this report is being formally transmitted to the European Ombudsman's office through their complaint process, to ensure they have the opportunity to acknowledge the documented failures and respond substantively to the main arguments concerning their operations. It will also be uploaded to the Zenodo repository. If any response arrives, that response will also be uploaded to the same Zenodo repository to ensure that the government has an opportunity to reply and everyone has the opportunity to be updated on following resolutions and declarations.

I am confident that the fact that I followed all available routes will make this whistleblowing action my last resort to expose a systemic problem related to innovation and the public domain, and avoid the risk of silence toward a problem that affects us all. In any case, I am sure this report will provide a useful case study to highlight major challenges in sustainable innovation.

Future actions will include the request for a petition to highlight important challenges to Europe in relation to innovation, sustainability, and abuse of power. This is relevant to the principle of research integrity that underlies our institutions and universities.

I will conclude with a statement from Jesus. I am not particularly religious, but there are those who suggest Jesus was a whistleblower.

“Father, if you are willing, take this cup from me; yet not my will, but yours be done” (Luke 22:42)

Yours faithfully,

Luca Danieli

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Statement of Reasoning for Public Disclosure

This document is being released publicly as a necessary and final measure of whistleblowing due to the systematic failure of the relevant European Union institutions to address reports of maladministration and abuse of power.

1. **Exhaustion of Internal Remedies:** The applicant followed all available formal routes, including the submission of a detailed redress request to the EACEA MEDIA Strand and a subsequent complaint to the European Ombudsman.
2. **Institutional Silence and Stonewalling:** Both the EACEA and the Ombudsman's office maintained a pattern of dismissal based on unsupported speculation and inadequate reasoning, thereby violating the applicant's right to good administration and preventing a fair investigation into demonstrable procedural errors and alleged abuse of power. Further requests of clarification have remained unresponded.
3. **Breach of Public Interest:** The subject matter directly concerns the integrity of EU research funding and poses a strategic threat to the Union's stated goals for Sustainable Development (SDGs) and innovation. The repeated failure to ensure fair evaluation of a project highly recognized by EU-affiliated initiatives constitutes a matter of high public concern.
4. **Legal Justification:** Pursuant to the principles of public disclosure for whistleblowers whose internal reporting has been exhausted or met with inaction, this action is taken to break the institutional silence and force accountability, making the evidence available to the public and all relevant oversight bodies. This disclosure is mandatory to serve the collective future and uphold the principles of research integrity and EU governance.

Review of the Applicant’s Core Arguments Informing a Complaint to the Creative Innovation Lab 2021, Regarding a Proposal Rejection

The current report investigates the results and subsequent reviews related to the rejection of a project proposal (ID: 101059555. Title: Marte) submitted by the applicant to the Creative Innovation Lab 2021, with a deadline in October 2021 and a decision issued in February 2022. As the applicant highlighted by citing a European Union website, the core objectives of the call were described as:

“Cross-sectoral cooperation within the creative and/or cultural sectors, including the audiovisual sector is at the heart of the call.” (see Figure 1)

Figure 1. Core objectives of the call.

An analysis of the provided description suggests:

- 1) The presence of a main theme of evaluation (**cross-sectoral cooperation**), and
- 2) A major requirement for eligibility (**the project must address both the creative/cultural AND the audiovisual sectors simultaneously / the audiovisual sector must be included**).

The applicant's project proposal received positive comments regarding the theme of evaluation (potential for cross-sectoral collaboration) but received a strong negative comment concerning the eligibility requirement, stating that the integration of the audiovisual sector in the product concept was not demonstrated. The reviewer's comment stated:

"There is a good level of innovation and potential for cross-sectoral collaboration, however the application fails to demonstrate how the audiovisual sector is integrated in the concept."

The applicant complained that the audiovisual sector **was, in fact, integrated**, and that the reviewer's statement was a demonstrable factual error that fully disqualified the project from funding. This was because the comment stated that the minimum and most important requirement for receiving funding was not satisfied, thereby impacting the application **substantially**.

The evidence provided by the applicant to support this claim was that the application contained a section called "**Product concept**," which referenced one main cross-sectoral organization to explain the concept: **The Science Gallery**. This cross-sectoral organization was considered a perfect fit for the call, as it produced outputs that mix cultural/creative and audiovisual content. The applicant's argumentation consisted of observing how this organization was considered part of the cultural/creative sectors, thus fully demonstrating their integration to the reviewer. **It followed that if** such an organization was also considered part of the audiovisual sector, it fully demonstrated the integration of the audiovisual sector. The applicant suggested that this error was due to a possible implicit bias of the reviewer, who may not have considered The Science Gallery as part of the audiovisual sector.

The final review of the applicant's redress request by the Head of Unit (HoU) of the Creative Europe MEDIA Strand **indeed confirmed** that The Science Gallery should be considered part of the audiovisual sector, stating:

"It is correct that you mention the experience of The Science Gallery and IRCAM."

The problem highlighted by the applicant through his complaint can therefore be represented through the following logic table:

Table 1. Representation of an illogical reasoning related to the complaint and following reviews.

	Cultural/creative sectors	Audiovisual sectors
Are The Science Gallery and IRCAM part of this sector?	Yes	Yes
Is this sector integrated in the concept?	Yes	No

In their response, the HoU **did not clearly address** the applicant's complaint about the integration of the audiovisual sector, nor did they clarify whether the audiovisual sector **should have been considered** integrated. Instead, the HoU responded by suggesting that the reviewer's comment **only implied** that the integration of the audiovisual sector lacked details.

The applicant reported this episode to the European Ombudsman, requesting an investigation into both the presence of procedural irregularities and abuse of power, which is defined by Europe as “lack or inadequate reasoning of the conclusions” for *Complaints About Proposal Rejection*.¹

¹ European Union. (n.d.). *Complaints About Proposal Rejection*. Available at: <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/display/OM/Complaints+about+proposal+rejection>.

Analysis of Core Arguments and Responses by the EU Institutions

The applicant requested access to his files under **Regulation 1049/2001**. In light of this information, which presents the underlying reasoning adopted by the EU institutions when dealing with the complaint, the following evidence can be observed.

- 1) It appears that the European Ombudsman dismissed valid arguments provided by the applicant based on **non-evidential speculation**.

The applicant reports that he originally submitted a redress request to the official email address of the Creative Innovation Lab program. After highlighting his concerns about the reviewer's comment and requesting a re-evaluation of the project proposal due to a factual error, the manager of the Creative Innovation Lab responded by stating that a **sub-restriction of content** informed the call for proposals. The CILab manager responded:

“Based on the Basic act and 2021 Work Programme, the “audiovisual sector” targeted by the MEDIA programme covers all activities and companies related to the development, production, distribution, promotion and circulation of the following content:

- Feature films, animations and creative documentaries intended primarily for cinematic release;
- Fiction audiovisual works (one-off or series), animation (one-off or series) and creative documentaries (one-off or series) intended primarily for the purposes of television or digital platform exploitation;
- Interactive, non-linear fiction, animation or creative documentary projects (e.g. narrative virtual reality projects);
- Narrative video games and interactive narrative immersive experiences. In order to be considered narrative, the story must be told or shown throughout the whole game (in-game storytelling) or interactive immersive experience, and not only as an introduction or an ending.”

In relation to the applicant's complaint, which highlighted that this sub-restriction was not reported in the guidelines, the European Ombudsman observed in their notes:

“While it is true that there is no single definition of ‘audiovisual’ in the 2021 WP, the eligibility can indeed be found in the legal base of the call for proposal (The 2021 Work Programme for Creative Europe and its MEDIA Strand)”

This statement by the European Ombudsman is demonstrably **incorrect**. There is no evidence in the 2021 Work Programme (WP)² that the set of restrictions/definitions mentioned by the CILab manager inform the **entire MEDIA Strand**. These specific restrictions are not part of a **Quadro** implementation but refer to specific calls run within the **Content Cluster** for 2021. From a legal perspective, they inform only a sub-group of calls (1.1, 1.2, 1.3, and not 1.4) in the Content Cluster, and there is no evidence to suggest these restrictions, specifically informing calls 1.1, 1.2, and 1.3, should be extended to other calls (while those for call 1.4 should not). It is also not evident why other eventual restrictions informing calls in other Clusters of the MEDIA Strand (e.g., Business Cluster, Audience Cluster) should not be subjected to the same reasoning.

The inapplicability of such restrictions to the Creative Innovation Lab becomes clear if the 2021 Work Programme is represented through the organizational tree available in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Tree representation of the 2021 Work Programme for Creative Europe.

² European Commission. (2021). *2021 annual work programme for the implementation of the Creative Europe Programme*. Available at: https://culture.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2021-05/creative-europe-2021-work-programme-c2021-3563_WP.pdf.

In particular, the European Ombudsman accepted all **the applicant's** observations, stating that:

- The unavailability of relevant assessment criteria in the guidelines would constitute a **manifest error**.
- No definition for the term “audiovisual” exists.
- Such restrictions were not provided in the 2021 guidelines but were introduced only from 2022.

However, the Ombudsman concluded that an eventual manifest error was not present because, given the CILab manager’s statement, it was **possible** for the applicant “to understand what was meant.” This assumption unfortunately **lacks evidence**. Under this assumption, the European Ombudsman expected the applicant to:

- 1) Read not only the Quadro implementation for the 2021 WP but **all the calls** of both the CULTURE and MEDIA Strand.
- 2) From there, selectively identify **only the calls** of the Content Cluster and ignore the calls and relative restrictions of both the CULTURE Strand and other Clusters of the MEDIA Strand (e.g., Business Cluster, Audience Cluster, etc.).
- 3) From there, selectively identify **only the restrictions** informing calls 1.1, 1.2, and 1.3, and ignore the restrictions of call 1.4.
- 4) Infer that such selective restrictions (and not others) would inform the selection criteria of the CILab.

If not impossible, this demand poses **unrealistic expectations** on the applicant. As they only inform a sub-group of calls of the Content Cluster, it is arguable that they were incorrectly mentioned by the CILab manager, providing a misleading argument.³

Furthermore, it must be noted that when citizens contact supporting staff working for the Creative Europe Desks, they are generally informed that if information is not reported in the guidelines, it does not apply (see Figure 3). By suddenly demanding that the applicant had to: (i) read all the calls informing the 2021 Work Programme, (ii) autonomously select specific restrictions informing specific calls, and (iii) infer that they informed a call in a different strand, this seems an attempt to place the responsibility on the applicant.

³ Curiously, while the initial reply of the manager of the Creative Innovation Lab placed emphasis on such restrictions in response to the applicant's complaint, and the European Ombudsman confirms the applicability of such restrictions, the European Ombudsman also highlights that the subsequent response by the HoU clarified that such restrictions did not penalize the application. The question therefore remains: why did the CILab manager mention them in the first instance?

R: Informazioni costi di subcontracting CILab

From: [REDACTED]
Date: Mon 27/09/2021 15:51
To: Luca Danielli [REDACTED]

Ciao Luca,
corretto, se non è indicato nelle linee guida non è richiesto.
Un saluto
[REDACTED]

Da: Luca Danielli [REDACTED]
Inviato: lunedì 27 settembre 2021 10:59
A: [REDACTED]
Oggetto: Re: Informazioni costi di subcontracting CILab

Cara [REDACTED]

una velocissima domanda: da come mi sembra di interpretare il bando Creative Innovation Lab, per essere beneficiari del finanziamento **non** bisogna avere un'attività/partita iva da almeno 2 anni. Dico bene, o sbaglio? Il requisito dei 2 anni è solo per i settori cultura e media?

Un saluto
Luca

Figure 3. Response from an officer of the Creative Europe Desk Italia.

Other observations lead to this conclusion:

- For example, nowhere in the Creative Innovation Lab is it written that activities shall be limited to contents produced in 2021, eventually ignoring content produced in the preceding years.
- The European Ombudsman does not account for the objectives and nature of the Creative Innovation Lab, which explicitly promotes **“innovative approaches to content creation.”** This directly contradicts the presence of restrictions on types of content, as the sentence calls for initiatives that transcend boundaries. It is therefore unclear why the applicant should have considered that such innovative approaches to content creation should be limited by restrictions from a sub-group of calls informing the Content Cluster of the MEDIA Programme.
- The CILab manager deemed the consortium to include expertise in the audiovisual sector, even though the consortium's expertise did not specifically or clearly align with the manager's own stated restrictions (e.g. narrative/fictional audiovisual).

The overall assessment is that, despite the applicant's argument that the audiovisual sector was included, both the Creative Innovation Lab and the European Ombudsman responded with speculation based on non-evidential proof. On the one hand, the Creative Innovation Lab introduced a set of restrictions without evidence for them to pertain to the Creative Innovation Lab call. On the other hand, the European Ombudsman demanded an

unrealistic expectation from the applicant, without considering the circumstantial properties of such restrictions (e.g., not part of a Quadro implementation). By resolving the issue of "manifest error" through this speculation/unrealistic expectation, the Ombudsman bypasses the need to investigate the fact that the applicant was provided with a set of **post-hoc restrictions** which did not clearly pertain to the call, making the response of the CILab manager misleading.

- 2) It appears that the European Ombudsman failed to acknowledge that the complainant's core argument remained unaddressed and therefore to investigate the **adequacy of reasoning** and evidence leading to rejection.

On February 2, 2023, the Head of EACEA B exceptionally allowed the applicant to submit his claims regarding the rejection of the proposal, which were subsequently evaluated by the Head of Unit (HoU) of the MEDIA Strand.

To summarize, the core argument provided by the applicant was that the audiovisual sector was **integrated**. If The Science Gallery (reported in the section "Product Concept") was operating in the audiovisual sector, the audiovisual sector should have been deemed included and demonstrated, since those entities were already considered to demonstrate the integration of the cultural/creative sectors.

In their response, the HoU acknowledged that The Science Gallery was indeed considered part of the audiovisual sector. However, instead of clarifying whether this implied that the audiovisual sector was indeed integrated, as the applicant's core argument demanded, the HoU approached the problem by means of a **double negative**, stating that the reviewer's comment did **not** mention that the audiovisual sector was **not integrated**. The response of the HoU stated:

"Firstly, the rejection letter you received states very precisely: "there is a good level of innovation and potential for cross-sectoral collaboration, however the application fails to demonstrate how the audiovisual sector is integrated in the concept" (emphasis added). As it is evident, there is absolutely no mention that the audiovisual sector is not integrated in your project. [...] In this respect, the sentence "the application fails to demonstrate how the audiovisual sector is integrated in the concept" only suggests that your application suffers from a lack of precision and details in describing the conditions of integration of the audiovisual sector into your project. [...] Indeed, in your application reference is essentially made to Cultural or creative sectors, without precisely defining how your project intends to integrate the audiovisual sector and respond to its specificities. In this respect, as mentioned in your letter, it is correct that you mention the experience of The Science Gallery and IRCAM."

This response from the HoU, however, presents a number of problems from a perspective of integrity:

- 1) **Unproven Speculation:** Within the scope of a proposal, the sentence, "however the application fails to demonstrate how the audiovisual sector is integrated in the concept," does not specify the reasons for the lack of demonstration. When the HoU states that it "**only suggests**" a lack of details, this is **speculation**, and no evidence is provided to support this claim. Lack of details can be one reason, but not the only one. Indeed, another potential reason, as argued by the applicant, is that the reviewer did not consider The Science Gallery to be part of the audiovisual sector. There is no sign in the reviewer's comments that the audiovisual sector was considered at least **partially integrated**, and the negative assessment may stem from an error or personal bias in not classifying The Science Gallery (and other networks like S+T+ARTS or EASTN-DC) as representatives of the audiovisual sector. Furthermore, the second reviewer did not highlight this critical lack of integration.
- 2) **Denial of Meaning/Impact:** Although the same sentence does not directly mention, from a grammatical perspective, that the audiovisual sector is not integrated, the only inference that can be drawn is that, overall, within the present application, the audiovisual sector must be considered as **not fulfilling the minimum requirements** of the call, and therefore must be considered as not integrated within the scope of the program. When the HoU states that there is no mention that the audiovisual sector is not integrated, the HoU attempts to reframe the meaning and diminish the impact of the sentence by exploiting grammatical nuances.⁴
- 3) **Failure to Address Core Question:** The HoU fails to clarify if the audiovisual sector was integrated in the concept. The HoU capitalizes on a double negative to state that the audiovisual sector was not "not-integrated." However, the core argument of the complaint was that the audiovisual sector was **fully integrated**. The response to the core question, "is the audiovisual sector integrated?," remains unaddressed.⁵

The HoU's response constitutes an example of **inadequate reasoning** because it fails to address the applicant's core logical argument: if the HoU confirmed The Science Gallery and IRCAM are part of the audiovisual sector, it logically follows that the audiovisual sector

⁴ The impact of such a comment on the overall score/evaluation is clarified by the reviewer themselves, as the reviewer explicitly states the non-integration of the audiovisual sector to be a "critical point."

⁵ The argument states: "Since The Science Gallery was operating in the audiovisual sector, it should prove the integration of the audiovisual sector exactly as it proves the integration of the cultural/creative sectors. Why was the lack of details argued only for the audiovisual sector and not for the cultural/creative sectors?"

should be deemed integrated, just as the cultural/creative sectors were. Otherwise, it is not clear why only the audiovisual sector should be deemed not integrated.

By failing to explain this logical inconsistency, avoiding direct clarification of whether the audiovisual sector was indeed integrated in the concept through the use of a double negative,⁶ and basing the entire justification on the non-evidential speculation that the comment "only suggests" a lack of details, the HoU's review did not provide a coherent or honest resolution to the complaint.

This inadequate reasoning is precisely what the EU web page on *Complaints About Proposal Rejection* describes as an instance of **abuse of power**, which the European Ombudsman subsequently failed to acknowledge. Specifically, the European Ombudsman fails to acknowledge the **lack of logical flow** (e.g., avoiding responding to the core argument raised by the applicant: is the audiovisual sector integrated?) and the **lack of evidence** supporting the reasoning of the HoU. The European Ombudsman responded:

“The answer of the [HoU] seems reasonable. It explains that the complainant has not been penalised due to his activities not being considered in line with the audiovisual activities of the program.”

However, this sentence written by the European Ombudsman cannot be supported by evidence. The assumption that the applicant's activities were not penalised for not being in line with the audiovisual activities of the program is unsupported speculation, as the comments of the reviewers do not provide this information and **leave open the possibility that the activities of the applicant may have been** considered as **not** in line with the audiovisual activities of the program, penalizing the application substantially.

The European Ombudsman eventually clarified that the claim that the lack of integration of the audiovisual sector was due to the lack of granular detail should be considered a **qualitative assessment** and not something the European Ombudsman could take a view on. This is incorrect, because this lack of detail was never mentioned by the reviewer and there is no evidence supporting this statement from the HoU. It is also incorrect as a general reason, as the definition of **power abuse** as “lack or inadequate reasoning of the conclusion,” reported on the web page *Complaints About Proposal Rejection*, automatically implies the possibility to contest qualitative judgments that are unsupported by evidence.

⁶ The HoU's statement: "there is absolutely no mention that the audiovisual sector is not integrated in your project," is a rhetorical deflection that employs a double negative. This device avoids answering the direct question posed by the applicant ("Is the audiovisual sector integrated?"), instead focusing on what the original reviewer *failed to say* (i.e., failed to use an explicit negative). This evasion serves as the clearest evidence of inadequate reasoning, as the HoU uses linguistic nuance to avoid providing a definitive, reasoned ruling on the core, substantive claim of the complaint.

Individual Reviews

Reviewer 1:

The parameters for the evaluation of the proposal in relation to **Criterion 1—Relevance**, are provided as **follows**:

“1.1. The relevance of the project to address the new market needs and find solutions applicable across sectors fostering cooperation, to improve the competitiveness of the European audiovisual and other cultural/creative sectors, as well as to increase the circulation, visibility, availability, diversity and audience of European content in the digital age.

1.2. The European dimension/potential of the project (including origin of the content and/or nature of the partnership and/or the cross-border and cross-language dimension and/or the potential for European expansion...).

1.3. Adequacy of the strategies to ensure gender balance, inclusion, diversity and representativeness, either in the project/content or in the way of managing the activity.”

The reviewer's comments for Criterion 1 included the following text:

“The application provides a very detailed description of the proposed action, which has a good level of innovation and potential for cross-sectoral collaboration, in particular for performing arts, music, theatre, artistic events. However, the application fails to demonstrate how the audiovisual sector is integrated in the concept.

Another critical point - new market needs are well presented (context of continuous reduction of funding for culture by national authorities in the last decade), however it is unclear what is the actual demand from audiences in rural areas, small towns and suburbs for this kind of service.”

The comments of the reviewer suggest two additional points:

- 1) The cultural and creative sectors were demonstrably integrated, particularly the field of music. Beyond the cross-sectoral network The Science Gallery, there are no organizations in the Product Concept strictly working in the field of music. It is therefore **unclear** why the reviewer considered the integration of the field of music to be demonstrated while not the field of audiovisual. Furthermore, a footnote provided the reviewer with a link redirecting to the *Earth Water Sky* program of The Science Gallery, where the following description was provided: “Every year there

will be an open call for artists from any art form – digital arts, painting, sculpture, dance, performance, music, multimedia, video, film, [etc.]”⁷

Through a keyword search, it is possible to identify only the following text mentioning the word “music” within the Product Concept, referring to The Science Gallery:

“As an example, musical works in the field of electroacoustic music may include experimentations connected to either the fields of “classical music”, “soundscape”, or “art-science”, as well as “audio-visual” experimentations.”

It is unclear why this statement should demonstrate the integration of the cultural and creative sectors (e.g., musical field) but not the inclusion of the audiovisual sector, as requested by the call. This suggests that if The Science Gallery was accepted as sufficient evidence for the cultural/creative sectors or music, it should logically have provided equivalent demonstration for the audiovisual sector, given that the HoU later deemed it audiovisual.

- 2) When the reviewer starts the second paragraph by including the sentence “Another critical point,” the reviewer clearly indicates that the lack of integration of the audiovisual sector had **substantial weight**.

Reviewer 2:

The comments of Reviewer 2 for Criterion 1 consisted of the following text (full excerpt):

“The relevance of the project is clearly defined, as it bridges the gap between emergent cultural production and audiences, particularly those in rural areas, with the use of an innovative digital tool based on big data analysis. The proposed solution has a strong cross-sectoral approach and promotes the visibility and interaction of European cultural and creative sectors. The market needs have been addressed clearly and the proposed digital platform has high scalability. The geographical distribution of the partnership could have been more diverse.”

Based on these comments, Reviewer 2 evaluated Criterion 1 with the following scores::

- Criterion 1.1 = 16/20.
- Criterion 1.2 = 10/15.
- Criterion 1.3 = 4/5.

⁷ The website is accessible through the Internet Archive WayBackMachine at link: “<https://venice.sciencegallery.com/earth-water-sky>”.

The application was not provided with this review at the time of rejection, and this review shows a new problem: given that there are no critiques for Criterion 1.1 and 1.2, and the project reports to have a strong cross-sectoral approach and high scalability, **why were 9 points taken away** from the relative scores?

This is a concrete example of **incoherence between scores and comments**, which is also reported as an accepted reason for redress, as shown on the web page *Complaints About Proposal Rejection*:

“Thus, applicants can raise procedural irregularities, factual errors, manifest errors of assessment or abuse of powers (*e.g. lack of coherence between scores and comments, lack or inadequate reasoning of the conclusions, the existence of a conflict of interests, exceeding the limits of discretion, etc.*)”

The failure to disclose this review deprived the applicant of the possibility to highlight this substantial incoherence that strongly penalized the application.

Conclusions

A number of observations emerge from the current investigation. It must be noted that both reviews included a form of **unmotivated penalties** that strongly affected the overall evaluation. In one instance, the applicant highlighted a factual error, specifically the lack of integration of the audiovisual sector observed by the first reviewer. In the other instance, a lack of coherence between scores and comments was observed, but the applicant was not given the opportunity to respond to this potential problem, which Europe itself highlights as a valid reason for redress. In both cases, the observed errors substantially penalized the overall score. It is a question whether, for public transparency, applicants should be provided with the original reviews.

The full complaint process managed by the EACEA and the European Ombudsman presents elements of basing judgments on speculation. Overall, the episode demonstrates clear **institutional resistance** to the applicant's core arguments, characterized by the contradictory tactic of first citing a set of restrictions and then later asserting those same restrictions did not penalize the proposal, followed by the reliance on a double negative.

In the case of the EACEA, the initial response from the Creative Innovation Lab manager introduced a set of restrictions that were not provided in the guidelines, and which affected only a subgroup of calls within the Content Cluster of the 2021 MEDIA program. It is unclear whether there are legal grounds to support the statement that such restrictions should inform the Creative Innovation Lab call, which the European Ombudsman clarified did not penalize the application. This is further strengthened by the fact that the CILab call intended to promote innovative approaches to content creation, suggesting the program may have aimed to promote new experimentation that transcended the content type restrictions mentioned by the CILab manager. This observation is particularly important as the European Ombudsman based their judgment on the assumption that it was possible for the applicant to understand that such restrictions applied to the call, a claim which this information seems to contradict.

Secondly, when called to review the complaint, the HoU used a double negative to claim that the audiovisual sector was mentioned by the reviewer as "not not-integrated." However, by doing so, the HoU failed to clarify if the audiovisual sector had to be considered integrated, as argued by the applicant. This type of rhetorical device creates the paradox that the audiovisual sector is simultaneously **not integrated** and **not not-integrated** in the concept, which constitutes a non-sense, and presents strong evidence for labeling the reasoning as **inadequate**. The statement that the reviewer's comment "only suggests" lack of detail is unsupported by evidence.

In the case of the European Ombudsman, the applicant originally submitted a complaint regarding two problems: the first consisted of the sudden apparition of a restriction in accepted audiovisual content that, if true, would have highlighted a manifest error. The European Ombudsman confirmed that, if true, a manifest error would be present. When reviewing the matter, the Ombudsman placed an unrealistic burden on the applicant to confirm the eligibility criteria. This ruling is somewhat paradoxical, given that the Ombudsman simultaneously declared that these restrictions did not penalize the application, raising questions about why they were introduced by the Creative Innovation Lab manager in the first instance.

The second problem consisted of the possible lack or inadequate reasoning in the rejection of a project proposal by the Head of Unit (HoU). In this case, the European Ombudsman did not ask for evidence supporting the HoU's speculation that the reviewer's comment "only" suggested lack of details, and failed to acknowledge that the HoU's response did not address the core argument of the complaint (whether or not the audiovisual sector was integrated in the concept), creating an illogical flow for which the audiovisual sector was simultaneously considered both **not integrated** and **not not-integrated**.

Although the involved staff or organizations may have created this paradox **unintentionally**, my role is to highlight the **logical inconsistency** that these institutions failed to address appropriately. This inconsistency lies in the fact that, while the reviewer may have genuinely believed the application lacked detail—perhaps by not classifying The Science Gallery as audiovisual—logically, the organization's content aligns with the definition of the audiovisual sector and should have resulted in the sector being considered integrated, particularly given its **crucial impact**, since the comment disqualifies the project from funding. This core argument was never substantively resolved. The easiest way to approach the core argument would therefore be to ask: "Is The Science Gallery integrated in the concept?" If the answer was yes, and if The Science Gallery was accepted as an example of the audiovisual sector, the application should have met the requirement. **This critical point should have been addressed by both institutions.** Otherwise, innovation risks being perpetually stifled by reviewer errors or personal biases.

The European Ombudsman, in particular, chose not to open an inquiry based on a "no grounds" justification; therefore, it gathered no evidence or information in relation to the applicant's complaint. Despite this, there is evidence showing that the treatment of the applicant's complaint presents instances of maladministration (e.g., the unclear dynamics by which a set of restrictions was mentioned by the CILab manager in response to the applicant's complaint) or power abuse (e.g., the presence of an illogical conclusion by the HoU and lack of evidence informing the statement about lack of details).

Implications for Integrity, Innovation, and Sustainable Development

The episode highlights bigger challenges for research and innovation in Europe that should be promptly addressed by the European Union. It highlights important concerns regarding the handling of reports of power abuse in research funding. At this point, it is unclear whether instances of power abuse, as described on the European web page *Complaints About Proposal Rejection*, should inform the actions of the European Ombudsman or those of other agencies. This ambiguity is particularly relevant to the principle of **integrity** that informs the European Union, and since the episode concerns a Research and Development (R&D) context, it extends to the field of **research integrity** in Europe.

The fact that two institutions engaged in the dismissal of a logical argument through unsupported speculation (e.g., inadequate reasoning from the HoU, unrealistic expectations from the European Ombudsman) raises concerns about whether this type of behavior characterizes European organizations at multiple levels. This would risk leaving citizens who cannot hire a lawyer vulnerable to forms of abuse of power and unfairness.

The episode is particularly concerning in relation to innovation policies centered on **Sustainable Development**, which also characterized the goals of the Creative Innovation Lab (with specific reference to the New European Bauhaus).

Indeed, the project proposal referred to a startup idea that was highly recognized: it was among the **top-9 international projects** evaluated by the Horizon-2020 CLIC Startup Competition (organized by the Italian National Research Council), the **top-14 Italian projects** in all sectors selected by the Innovability School of the Italian Alliance for Sustainable Development, and the **top-4 European projects** in the Cultural & Creative Industries (CCI) promoted by the Startup Europe Accelerathon. Startup Europe Accelerathon is an initiative of the European Commission dedicated to identifying and promoting projects that align with European priorities (e.g., LIFE, New European Bauhaus, etc.).

The United Nations has highlighted that we will be reaching only 17%⁸ of planned SDGs targets, and that many of these targets are going in reverse. To reach our goals we need breakthrough innovation, particularly given the alarms about our lack of time. If promising projects risk being undermined by instances of abuse of power or unfairness, one must question whether we will ever reach our Sustainable Development Goals. The episode also brings light to the potential randomness in innovation selection. Specifically, one reviewer

⁸ The 2024 report by the UN reports 17% instead of the previously mentioned 15% by Guterres in 2023.

assigned substantially lower scores despite providing exclusively positive written feedback. This raises a critical question regarding the integrity and objectivity of the mechanisms used to correctly identify and select innovative projects in Europe. This concern is further supported by recent scientific studies highlighting a general decrease in breakthrough innovation after the 1970s.

To achieve sustainability, it is a prerogative for the European Union that promising projects are not sabotaged from within. Efforts must be made to ensure that projects that may have an impact in reaching our goals are not penalized due to maladministration or abuse of power. This episode shows that projects that experience these forms of unfairness may find it difficult to have their damage repaired. In such cases, less innovative projects may take priority. However, our shortage of time does not allow for this outcome, and Europe should prioritize ensuring that projects undergo a fair evaluation, both in respect to individual rights of fairness and to our collective goals.